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Sino-Indian Relationship In The Asian Age

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Abstract

India and china have historically maintained Peaceful relation for thousands of year. But the harmony of their relationship has varied in modern times, after the Chinese Communist Party victory in the Chinese civil war in 1949 and specially post the Chinese Annexation of Tibet by the people Republic of China. The Silk Road not only served as a major trade route between India and China.

Keywords India and China, Chinese Civil War, Sino-Indian Relationship.

Introduction

India and China, the two Asian giants, consisting of 1/3 population, are neighbours having a shared history of more than 3000 years. Relationship in ancient time was marked by trade relations through the famous 'Silk Route' and cultural relations particularly the impact of Buddhism on Chinese people. In fact, it was the charm and fascination of Buddhism that inspired the Chinese pilgrims to visit India while facing tremendous difficulties en route. In return, many Indian monks and pilgrims also paid visits to China. There were fewer contacts between India and China during the medieval time but the trade relations between India and China continued unabated. We do have witness of East India Company's monopoly over the trade with China that was in tea in particular.

Objective of study

The main objectives are :

1. To analyze the historical relation between India and China.
2. India-china economic culture and religious aspect.

Review of Literature

Past studies on India-China relation earlier research are their gaps :

1. Historical relation
2. Trade relation
3. Panchshila principle

Main Text

India and China both began their journey as modern sovereign entities simultaneously. Pt. Nehru, who was the architect of Indian foreign policy, was mesmerized by the ideal of third world unity and had much appreciation for China as a result he extended his full support for India-China friendship which was to be major force in the ideologically divided world whereas China was skeptical about the Indian moves and motives. It rather termed India as a 'bourgeoisie country' and 'mouthpiece of imperial powers'. Pt. Nehru was criticized for being 'running dog of imperialism'. But gradually, the Chinese perception witnessed a change as Soviet Union's proximity with both the India and China.

India extended full support China to international arena; it advocated its entry in United Nations and voted against UN resolution branding China as an 'aggressor' in Korean crisis. This was the time of 'Hindi-Chini Bhai Bhai' days which culminated into numerous cultural and technical exchanges along with the high level political exchanges. In April 1954, an agreement was signed between the two countries whereby India gave up its extra-territorial rights in Tibet and recognized it as an autonomous part of China. Also, five principles of peaceful co-existence, better known as Panchsheel were enunciated

by the agreement to which both countries pledged to abide . Prime Minister Zhou-En Lai of China visited India in June 1954 just to be followed by the visit of Pt. Nehru to Chia in 1954. At that time only, both countries moved together to champion the cause of third world countries and it was explicit during the

'Bandung Conference' in 1955 where India whole heartedly supported the Chinese to come forward to take the leadership of the third world countries. Mao-Ze-Dong's theory of 'Intermediate Zones' and United Front' coupled with Nehru's policy of 'Non-Alignment' and Asian Solidarity' helped to strengthen the diplomatic ties.

However, this Euphoria soon took a back seat when mutual reservations began to be articulated openly. The Chinese imperial ambitions propelled to make cartographic aggression as well as territorial incursion into Indian territorial. Tibetan uprising of 1959 and the subsequent escape of Dalai Lama from Tibet and his asylum in India aggravated the apprehensions of the Chinese. Meanwhile, the border problem took serious turn and as a consequence, both countries started to position troops in the disputed area. Meeting of Zhou-En Lai and Pt. Nehru in 1960 resulted in absolute failure. Zhou proposal was put forward by Chinese Prime Minister but was rejected by India.

In 1962, India adopted forward policy establishing a military presence in the disputed Aksai-China area. In October 1962, a war break out which ended with Beijing's unilateral declaration of ceasefire on November 21 and withdrawal to position 20 km behind the LAC that existed in 1959. Diplomatic relations came to a halt in 1976 and remained frozen till 1976. Meanwhile, the cultural revolution in China adversely affected the bilateral relations. Both countries indulged in propaganda war against each other. During the same period, the open rift between Soviet Union and China occurred, which helped India to forge closer ties with Soviet Union and China, strengthened the 'all-weather friendship' with Pakistan in 1960s. But, even, in this period of sharp hostility and mistrust, few incidents took place which indicate the mood of two countries to initiate normalization of relations. But it was not earlier than 1976 that ambassadorial-level relationship was re-established. It was in 1979, A.B.Vajpayee, as External Affairs Minister, went to Beijing and met his Chinese counterpart Huang Hua. He also had discussions with the paramount leader Deng-Xiao-Ping. Both sides emphasized the importance of preserving peace and tranquility along the LAC. China accepted Indian request of the pilgrimage route to Kailash Mansarovar. But, Mr. Vajpayee had to cut short his visits as the Vietnam War broke out. In 1981, following India's initiative towards restoring ties, Huang Hua, the Chinese Vice Premier, visited India. The Border Talks started in 1981 and continued till 1988, involving 8 rounds of talk. However, these talks could not produce any solutions of the border problem. Still, its importance in improving bilateral relations as providing platform to bilateral talks to resolve the vexed India-China border problem cannot be neglected.

The path-breaking visit of Rajiv Gandhi to China took place in 1988. During his visit, both sides made firm resolve to adhere to the Panchsheel, the Five Principles of Peaceful Co-existence. Both sides pledged to work together to realize the dream of making 21st century as an ASIAN century. One significant result of this visit was in the form of Joint Working Group, (JWG) which was established to resolve the border dispute and to maintain peace and tranquility along the border. In 1991, Li-Peng, the then Chinese Prime Minister paid a return visit to India. Decision was taken to reopen the consulate offices in India and China. In September 1993, the then Indian Prime Minister P. V. Narasimha Rao visited the China in a very cordial and friendly atmosphere. One agreement on 'maintaining peace and stability' in the vicinity of the Line of Actual Control LAC was signed. In the end of 1996, Jiang Zemin, President of China, visited India. It was the visit of the topmost Chinese dignitary since the thaw in the diplomatic front. The highlight of the visit was the signing of a landmark agreement on Confidence-Building Measures (CBM) between the two countries along the disputed border. The agreement envisaged a reduction of forces deployed within mutually-agreed geographical zones. Moreover, Both countries agreed to stop flying combat aircrafts within 10 km of the LAC. To speed up the process of clarification of LAC, the two sides agreed to exchange maps. These would help them identify specific areas where troops are in close proximity to each other. Many other agreements were also signed. On the whole, this visit witnessed a positive change in Chinese behaviour for the good of India. Both sides expressed their commonality of views, as was evident in the speech of Jiang Zemin, " Our common interests far outweigh our differences, neither of us poses any threat to others". Both presidents underlined the cultural and historical greatness of the two countries and the cooperative role they would play in the world in the coming century.

In the may 1998, the Indian defence minister George Fernandes gave a statement regarding China as enemy number one of India. This statement was taken very seriously by the Chinese and the relations between the two countries suffered badly. This episode was not yet over that again. In May 1998, India conducted a series of nuclear explosion. The letter of Indian Prime Minister to American President, claiming that test were necessary in view of the presence of nuclear state (obviously China) which had committed aggression against India in 1962, further angered the Chinese. China criticized Indian tests vehemently. It seemed that bilateral relations came to a halt again. The JWG meeting was postponed and no diplomatic exchange took place for 8 months. Indian tests largely upset China's calculation. The Indian nuclear tests certainly compelled it to rethink its strategic perception. In February 1999, for the first time after the May

1998 impasse, senior Chinese and Indian officials met formally in Beijing. The main purpose of the meeting was to kick-start the JWG that had been stalled. During the visit of Jaswant Singh in 1999, both India and China initiated a security dialogue that encompassed the nuclear issue and both sides agreed to enhance mutual exchange of visits at various levels and boost bilateral trade and economic cooperation. In April 2000, China and India celebrated the 50 years of establishment of diplomatic relations and the 12th meeting of the JWG took place in New Delhi. President K. R. Narayanan visited China in May 2000 to mark the completion of the 50 years of India-China relation. The Indian President pressed for greater speed in completing stage first of the boundary resolution process, the task of delineating LAC that came into effect after 1962 conflicts. He said that the problems left over by history need not to be left for future generations, to be dealt later. China also criticized attack on Indian parliament and declined to demand to use its influence for resolving Kashmir problem. Chinese Premier Zhu Rongji visited India in January 2002, as many as six agreements were signed during his visits.

In the end of 2002, Hu Jintao became the new president and Wen Jiabao was appointed as new Prime Minister. In 2003, George Fernandes visited China. Most significant gain of the visit was 'Declaration of Principle for Relations and Comprehensive Cooperation' between People's Republic of China and Government of India. Both sides agreed to appoint special representatives, (SRs) to speed up talks over the border issue. In 2005 only, Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao visited India whereby the agreement on Strategic Partnership to resolve long-standing border problem was signed, which has far-reaching implications for both the countries. Year 2006 was commemorated as India China Friendship Year. In 2006, Nathu -La was opened as a trade route between two countries. The friendship year reached to its conclusion with the high-profile visit of Chinese President Hu Jintao to India. The visit aimed to enhance strategic and cooperative partnership. In October 2007, India's ruling coalition UPA Chairperson Sonia Gandhi paid a five-days visit to China, which further boosted the relations between India and China. The gesture shown indicated the level of importance China attached to her visit, as its top leaders normally and officially meet with other heads of state only. In 2007, the party leadership in China endorsed the present leadership for another five years, which means Hu Jintao would remain at the helm of affairs while continuing the policy of peaceful development of China. In 2007, the first joint anti-terrorism exercise 'Hand-in-Hand 2007' took place. Indian Prime Minister Manmohan Singh completed his much-awaited visit to China from January 13 to 15, 2008, marked by enthusiasm in relation to a new height. Again, economic issues took precedence over other issues, contentious issues such as the border problem were deliberately kept aside. Ten agreements on various issues were signed. Another outcome of the visit was the understanding reached for cooperation in the civilian nuclear supply. The two-sided pledged to promote bilateral cooperation in civil nuclear energy consistent with their respective international commitments. During this visit, China for the first time showed its willingness to support India's candidature for the permanent membership of the Security Council.

The most significant issue which has impacted the Sino-Indian relation in recent time is shift in Chinese policy towards Jammu and Kashmir. The issue was highlighted when the GOC Northern Command Lt. Gen. B. S. Jaiswal was denied visa. The explanation given was that he headed the army in Jammu and Kashmir which was a disputed area. Following the incident, all the defence exchanges between the both countries were suspended. It was a great setback to the relations which seemed to be on track. Chinese official also started to issue Staple Visa to the residents of Arunachal Pradesh. India protested several times but the Chinese authorities continued to issue Staple Visa. These incidents created an atmosphere of doubt, many others fuelled it. Following years saw both countries confronting each other on various fronts. Several incidents of Chinese troops crossing into Indian territory were reported from Ladakh. Although Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao visited India in December 2010 but nothing solid could be achieved. 2011 was not different one. Both .

countries found themselves engaged in a dogfight. The year started with concern in Indian security establishment over the presence of about 11,000 troops in POK. India protested the move. It was just the beginning. South China Sea became the new battleground. The issue came to surface when the oil sector giant ONGC through ONGC Videsh Ltd. Worked in collaboration with state-owned Vietnamese Company to explore oil and natural gas in the region. India said that its interests in South China Sea were purely commercial and country-specific. Another event that fuelled the row was the radio contact to INS Airawat by a caller identifying itself as Chinese Navy. The caller asked the ship to go away from the region as it was in Chinese territorial water. The Indian naval ship did not respond to the call and followed its path. In November, the meeting of special representatives (SRs) was cancelled. Reports surfaced in media that the dates of meeting coincide with that of a Buddhist conference in which Dalai Lama had to participate. The 20th round of meeting, then took place on January 10-12 October 2023. The last year of 2022 was in highlight due to another unfortunate reason Peyang jheel conflict and Galwan Ghanti 15 16 june 2020.

Conclusion

India and China, the two Asian giants, jointly account for two-third of world population and two-fifth of world geography. Together they are the major force in the free world and have the capacity to form a separate power bloc strong enough to thwart any challenge

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from any other country. Friendly relations between India and China are necessary not only for peace and stability in South Asia by in the world at large. The two neighbours should work together to usher in a new era marked by mutual trust, equality, mutual benefit, friendship and cooperation. They share common interests on issues as multipolarisation, globalization, human rights, climate change, terrorism, combating drug trafficking, crimes and population control. The 'Panchsheel' principle propounded by the leaders of the two countries could be the basis for bilateral relations as well as for the establishment of New International and Economic and Political Order. Both the countries have expressed their faith in the Panchsheel from time to time, but it is required not to indulge in diplomatic polemics but to implement these principles in their actual diplomatic discourses. There is a good scope for economic cooperation between India and China. The trade between the two countries rose to 125.62 billion \$ 2024. The trade to touch 87 billion \$

For now , both countries need to work on Confidence Building Measures (CBMs)so that concerns of each other can be addressed. There is enough space in present world order for India and China to co-exist. India should address Chinese concerns over Tibet and the South China Sea through proper diplomatic channels and media must not be given a free hand to spark the row. While China must address Indian concerns over Staple visa, trade deficits, its position on Jammu and Kashmir. A solution to the boundary dispute is the swap deal meaning "you keep what you have and we keep what we control". Tibet is the main cause of dispute between India and China. Although India has already recognized Tibet as an integral part of China but it is not comfortable with the activities of Dalai Lama in India. Although China had never put forth any condition regarding Tibet but it seems as if some hitch is there, which implies that China would resolve boundary issue only when it feels comfortable with Tibet. If it is not so, it would keep border problem continue and border talks to linger on without reaching to any conclusion. Therefore, it is imperative for both India and China to learn to live with peace and cooperation as it is well said. " You can change friends but you can't change neighbours."

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